

Of Qualia and the Nature of the Universe

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Abstract

In this note the author discusses the relation between qualia and the physical spatiotemporal universe.

In the context of nirvikalpa cognition [1], there is no such thing as red-“ness,” or any other quality of an object. Only the pure sensory universe exists. Thus there is no need to postulate consciousness as a medium or explanation for qualia [2]. Let us call “qual” the thing of which the qualia were generated. To reframe the above, only quals exist. Change is qualia of the universe or objects¹. Therefore change does not exist. Thus time which supposedly measures change does not have a reason to exist. To summarize,

- Qvals existing or, existence of universe as such, is the only constant.
- Every reference frame, or mindset, perceives the same existence or quals.

Let there be some quals and let the universe or a geometrical object G , be the collection of such quals. Let there be some reference frames as well where a reference frame gives a view from a part of G to the whole of G . Since every reference frame perceives the same existence or quals, then either the universe is fractal in nature with “position or direction-of-viewing” being the equivalent of “zooming-depth” of ordinary fractals, or the reference frames are equal. Another possibility is that the universe is a point, as only a point appears the same in all reference frames. This last implies that the universe has no spatial extent which contradicts the geometrical construction of G . Thus the quals cannot belong to any G . In short there are no quals and that implies no time and no space, or, alternately the presence of spacetime implies the presence of quals.

References

- [1] Bimal Matilal. *Logic, Language and Reality*. Motilal Banarsidass.
- [2] David J Chalmers. *Philosophy of mind: Classical and contemporary readings*. Oxford University Press, USA, 2002.

¹One can re-express it as “changefulness.”